

FACTORS INFLUENCING TO DEVELOP NATIONAL AND GENERAL CULTURAL COMPETENCIES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the factors that affect the development of national and general cultural competences in students of future teachers are studied, its necessity and pedagogical relevance today are covered in detail.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, national and general cultural competences.

INTRODUCTION. Today, about two thousand nationalities, peoples and tribes live in the countries of the world. They speak and communicate in about five and a half thousand languages. Communication is the basis of relations between nations and peoples. Language is the main tool in communication. However, until now, in the process of cultural communication between the countries, it is not a process of "mixing, mixing, merging", but rather an effort is being made to show one's own "I". There were times when nations and peoples became enemies and tried to destroy each other. History has also witnessed the struggle of nations for domination over each other and a massive world war. But social development has confirmed that the most important and effective way in the development of nations and peoples is the way of inter-ethnic communication.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of socio-cultural activity among future teachers in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, H. Tojiboyeva, G.J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasov regarding the development of socio-cultural competence; historical-philosophical, ethical-aesthetic content of spiritual and artistic values , O. Abdurakhmonov, D. Yakibova, R. Mavlonova, N. Rakhmonkulova have conducted studies on the development of thinking capabilities of learners based on the person-oriented approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. As a multinational country, Uzbekistan should pay special attention to the following universal principles recognized by the international community and treat them as a priority in the process of preparing future teachers for the process of developing their national and general cultural competence.

- recognition of mutual equality of nations;
- establishing international cooperation;
- to communicate taking into account national spiritual and cultural characteristics;
- treat all nations and peoples with respect;
- ensuring harmony of national and universal values in society.

Just as a person cannot live separately from others, nations and peoples cannot live separated and surrounded by other nations. A nation communicates with other nations, exchanges its own with the cultural achievements of other nations, shares experience and gradually improves. History has not witnessed the social development of any nation where Ayro lived. Therefore, interethnic communication is a historical and social necessity. Today, it is natural that any nation is ready to accept the experience of another nation and share the products of its civilization with other nations. This attitude towards other nations is called "inter-national dialogue".

Three factors stand out in the process of intercultural communication:

- communicative (information transfer)
- interactive (to act together)
- perspective (mutual perception) [2].

According to the conclusions of advanced international scientific research centers of the West, the formation of tolerance, endurance, and patience skills in future teachers can cause a radical change in the development of the growing intercultural conflicts in the next quarter [3]. Therefore, cultivating the following qualities in future teachers will develop intercultural communication skills in them and prevent the emergence of ethnic conflicts.

- accepting and respecting the diversity, color and uniqueness of the race, nation, people, culture, religion, language and countries of the world;
- to recognize and understand the existence of the unique value system, customs, logical thinking process, and lifestyle of people of other races, nations, peoples, cultures, religions, languages, and countries, to understand that this situation is natural;
- to accept the presence of different aspects of another person, regardless of his race, nationality, ethnicity, culture, religion, language, and state, and to have a positive attitude to the system of these differences;
- to rely on universal humanitarian criteria in the evaluation of his emotional and emotional aspects in relation to any person, to try to evaluate the

inner world of another person, to evaluate the feelings valued by another person;

- learning to solve problems on the basis of tolerance in various crisis and conflict situations, acquiring the necessary skills for successful solutions of conflicts based on tolerance and always following the requirements of tolerance [6].

In addition, there is a need to pay special attention to the following in the preparation of future teachers for the process of developing national and general cultural competence.

- future teachers should know the essence of the categories of intercultural communication and tolerance, the stages of their historical formation;

- students should know and correctly analyze the meaning of the terms "multiculturalism", "polyethnicity", "subculture", "monoculture" and "polyculture [4]";

- teach future teachers about such categories as "genocide, racism, xenophobia, extremism, ethnocentrism, fundamentalism, radicalism, nationalism, separatism, localism, national and group selfishness, religious fanaticism and religious hypocrisy [5]" understand and learn to evaluate and form philosophical thinking against them;

- to have knowledge about freedom of conscience and religious rights;

- in the conditions of intercultural conflict, at a time when the ideological struggle is intensifying, educating students as mature specialists with deep thinking and deep analytical skills;

- formation of skills to communicate with others based on the humanitarian point of view, not to cause them moral or physical harm [6]. Based on the above opinions, we tried to justify the social necessity of preparing future teachers for the process of developing national and general cultural competence with the following:

First of all, there is a social need to educate all science teachers in the spirit of national tolerance in a situation where inter-ethnic relations are becoming tense. In the process of globalization, in the conditions of the clash of nations and cultures, in the situation where the socio-cultural pressure of the strong culture on the weak cultures is being observed, in the era of the intensifying ideological influence of civilizational and religious struggles, educating a tolerant person and a tolerant specialist is becoming an urgent task. In the world, special attention is being paid to turning tolerance into the highest human virtue. It is no coincidence that UNESCO adopted the Declaration "On the

Principles of Tolerance" and that November 16 is widely celebrated as the International Day of Tolerance throughout the world, including in our country. As stated in this declaration: "There is no peace without tolerance, and without peace there is no development and democracy." Tolerance means respecting, accepting and understanding the different ways in which different cultures in our world express themselves and show their uniqueness. It creates knowledge, sincerity, open communication, free thinking, conscience and faith. Tolerance is unity in diversity. It is not only a duty, but also a political and legal necessity. Tolerance is a force that ensures the achievement of peace and leads from the culture of war to the culture of peace. Showing tolerance is not being indifferent to human rights or tolerant of social injustice, giving up one's faith and giving in to the beliefs of others. This means that everyone is free to practice their own beliefs, and everyone should recognize that others have this right as well. People differ in appearance, image, behavior, speech, behavior and values, they have the right to live in the world and preserve their individuality. It also means that one person's views cannot be forced upon others [7]. Therefore, in the preparation of future teachers for the process of developing national and general cultural competence, it is necessary to educate them in the spirit of tolerance.

Secondly, it is necessary to prepare future teachers to respect the national characteristics, values, customs and traditions of different nations and peoples. The future teacher is not only a pedagogue, but also a representative of one nation, a person who believes in one religion, enters into a cultural dialogue with a representative of another nation and religion. Taking into account the need for a person to respect the values, traditions and beliefs of another person from the point of view of humanity, the future teacher should be ready for intercultural relations as a communicator. For this, they should know the values and traditions of other nations and peoples, and form a scientific attitude towards them.

Thirdly, there is a need to develop the quality of religious tolerance by increasing their religious knowledge and forming their worldly knowledge about religions in preparing future teachers for intercultural communication. "Religious tolerance is not a concession or flattery to subversive groups, extremist organizations, terrorism or fundamentalism, but an approach and attitude to reality with deep thinking and worldly intelligence" [3]. Uzbekistan, as a secular state, separates religion from the state, religion does not interfere in political processes, and the state does not interfere in the affairs of religion and religious organizations. But this does not mean that religion and religious

institutions can do whatever they want. In every society, relations between the state and religion and religious organizations are regulated by law. In such a situation, everyone has the constitutional right to believe in any religion and respect religious values. Therefore, the tasks of teaching science teachers to respect the constitutional religious right of other nationalities and peoples, that faith should not be chosen by nationality, or ethnic identity, are emerging. The President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, expresses his opinion in this regard: "Due to the atmosphere of religious tolerance prevailing in our country, more than 2200 different religious organizations are operating in our country. Developing mutual respect and friendly relations between representatives of different religions, ensuring equal rights for citizens, regardless of their religion and belief, will continue to be one of our most important tasks. We have been strongly fighting against the destructive forces that are misinterpreting our holy religion and masking it, trying to bring us back to the life of the Middle Ages, and we will continue to fight hard" [1]. Taking into account the fact that inter-ethnic national and religious conflicts are caused by religious and secular ignorance, ignorance, narrow-mindedness and selfishness, the task of educating future teachers is becoming a necessity.

The success of the development of national and intercultural competence of future teachers depends on the consistency of the world and language models adopted by the participants of this process. To implement communicative intentions, partners use socio-cultural knowledge, practical communication skills. Today, there are no unanimous opinions on the purpose of teaching national and universal cultural heritage in the science of pedagogy.

Y. V. Begunova believes that the global goal of training future teachers on the basis of general cultural skills is to create conditions for the formation and development of a person capable of playing an active and creative role in the immediate environment, state and people's life, the entire human community.

Different views on this matter can be divided into the following groups:

- to educate students in the spirit of respect and love for their people and Motherland;
- education of patriotism, citizenship, formation of national consciousness, teaching to respect the historical and cultural heritage of one's country and the peoples of the whole world;
- formation of a citizen capable of living in a multicultural and pluralistic society;

- forming a humane person with a high culture, showing careful, valuable and active attitude to the world's spiritual and material-cultural heritage;
- respecting the memory of the past and establishing a personal emotional connection with the heritage of past generations;
- forming a kind and tolerant attitude towards other cultures and peoples;
- introducing a person to the cultural environment created by his compatriots and the whole of humanity and forming skills useful in social communication and public behavior;

- forming the student's personality and values, preparing him for life in a rapidly changing world, teaching the information society, its modern forms of communication, developing work skills and studying information, teaching effective decision-making. So, every idea has a socio-cultural component of education that develops national and universal skills. In this regard, the following definition of S.SH.Alimov is more reliable: national and general cultural competence of a teacher is an integral part of pedagogical competence, it is considered an integral characteristic of a specialist, and he has his own knowledge of national culture, language, religion. It requires readiness and abilities to apply comprehensive social and cultural knowledge of the country's education and pedagogy in the course of their professional activities. As a result, taking into account the changing socio-economic conditions and the general situation in the educational system, it is necessary to choose the most optimal options for organizing the pedagogical process, to predict its results, to navigate in time, to adapt to modern conditions, to anticipate difficult situations and there is a need for a future professional who is able to leave behind.

The preparation of future teachers for the development of national and general cultural competences in students depends on the following:

- characteristics of historical and cultural development of the society;
- the place of teachers as a social and professional community;
- the development of modern education as a socio-cultural phenomenon;
- specific characteristics of the socio-educational situation of a given educational environment;
- personal mechanisms of formation of professional activity;
- the teacher's assimilation of the humanistic paradigm of education and its implementation.

CONCLUSION. To determine the methods and possibilities of influencing the development of the personality and socio-educational situation of the future teacher-student, to study the specific characteristics of the teaching profession

and the factors that determine the professional and personal direction, the society it is required to be able to determine the suitability of social needs and professional role.

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